

Exploring Tipping Points and Their
Impacts Using Earth System Models

Policy briefing Nr 1

Deliverable D9.7

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1. Abstract

During the reporting period, TipESM contributed to two policy briefing events. The main TipESM policy briefing event was a side event during the 61st session of the UN Human Rights Council entitled “Human Rights and Tipping Points”, organised in collaboration with Just Atonement Inc. and the UN Special Rapporteur on Climate Change and Human Rights. In addition to this main event, TipESM also participated in a cluster science-policy forum with the European Commission, organised jointly with six related EU-funded projects. The first event was held in Geneva in March 2026, while the second took place in Brussels in September 2025. Both events and their outcomes are described below.

2. Work done

2.1 Policy briefing event at the UN Human Rights Council

The policy briefing event, titled “Human Rights and Tipping Points,” was held on 6 March 2026. The event took place during the 61st session of the UN Human Rights Council in Geneva, Switzerland. The event was organised in collaboration with Just Atonement Inc. and the UN Special Rapporteur on Climate Change and Human Rights.

Background

Recent developments in international law, including the 2025 Advisory Opinion of the International Court of Justice on climate change (1), the 2025 Advisory Opinion of the Inter-American Court of Human Rights on the climate emergency and human rights (2), and the 2024 Advisory Opinion of the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea related to climate change (3), represent significant legal milestones in affirming states’ obligations to prevent foreseeable climate-related harm. At the same time, these developments underscore the growing importance of collaboration between climate researchers and members of the legal community for achieving effective responses to the climate crisis. With the Paris Agreement (4) becoming increasingly recognised in legal proceedings as a legally binding aspect of international environmental law, climate change is becoming a major area of engagement for legal scholars, policymakers, and human rights experts. Discussions on the human rights implications of climate change are now a recurring feature of sessions of the United Nations Human Rights Council. Specifically, the rights to life, health, food, water and sanitation, work and livelihood, development, and even self-determination and cultural identity can all be

affected by climate change, particularly by crossing any of the major climate tipping points. Moreover, climate tipping points are also becoming recognised as a major risk to political and civil rights, democratic governance and the rights of future generations.

In June 2025, TipESM researcher Ivana Cvijanovic participated in the Global Climate Tipping Conference 2025 in Exeter, UK, in the session “Testing the Limits of International Law”, organised by Just Atonement Inc. Following this session, a series of online meetings was held with TipESM researchers, Just Atonement Inc., their network of human rights experts, representatives of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, and the Special Rapporteur on Climate Change and Human Rights. Building on their experience organising the event “Addressing the Point of No Return: Human Rights and Climate Tipping Points” at COP30 in Belém, Brazil, Just Atonement Inc. and the Special Rapporteur proposed a further collaboration with TipESM to organise a side event during the 61st Session of the Human Rights Council.

TipESM contributed three scientific presentations tailored for an audience composed of government representatives and civil society organisations (NGOs). Just Atonement Inc. moderated the event, while the Special Rapporteur on Climate Change and Human Rights and a representative of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights delivered the concluding remarks. Additional time was provided for the side event participants to interact and ask the presenters questions.

The event was designed to support Agenda Item 3 of the Human Rights Council: “Promotion and protection of all human rights, civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights, including the right to development.”

Objectives

The event sought to achieve the following key objectives:

- 1. Bridging science and law.** The event provided an opportunity for TipESM scientists to present current research on climate tipping points and to engage directly with participants through discussion and questions.
- 2. Exploring the human rights implications of climate tipping points.** Panellists examined the human rights dimensions of the risk of crossing climate tipping points, including implications for vulnerable populations, the rights of indigenous populations, and the protection of fundamental rights.

3. Examining governance challenges in the context of human rights. The discussion addressed gaps in existing governance frameworks, particularly at the intersection of climate tipping points, human rights obligations, and international accountability mechanisms.

Activity Description

The panel was moderated by Dave-Inder Comar, Executive Director of Just Atonement Inc. Presenting scientists from TipESM project included: Andrew Hartley (METO), introducing the concept of climate tipping points in the presentation: "[Global climate tipping points: What are they and what could they mean?](#)"; Desislava Petrova (ISGlobal), who discussed the risks of Amazon rainforest dieback in the presentation entitled: "[The Amazon: A potential tipping point for the Earth's climate system](#)"; and Ivana Cvijanovic (IRD), who presented an overview of current understanding of threats to human habitability arising from extreme heat while drawing comparisons with the existing legal frameworks addressing sea-level rise: "[Do we need a legal framework for loss of habitability due to extreme heat?](#)". Elisa Morgera, UN Special Rapporteur on the promotion and protection of human rights in the context of climate change and Benjamin Schachter from the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) served as discussants, providing additional legal and human rights perspectives on the implications of crossing climate tipping points.

In addition to being presented to representatives of countries and NGOs at the 61st Session of the UN Human Rights Council, the event was streamed online, with 15 attendees, including 2 DG RTD policy officers.

Key Discussion Outcomes

The discussion highlighted the growing need for sustained exchange between the climate research and legal communities. Participants repeatedly emphasised that opportunities for interdisciplinary dialogue on climate tipping points and human rights remain limited, underscoring the value of events that facilitate direct engagement between scientists, legal experts, policymakers, and civil society representatives. Specific topics discussed included: *monitoring of heat-related mortality, increased energy need for cooling, impacts of melting glaciers and energy safety, food security and loss and damage funds.*

Photo 1: Online view of the side event “Human Rights and Tipping Points” at the 61st session of the UN Human Rights Council in Geneva.

Government representatives from India and Pakistan expressed particular interest in the implications of extreme heat, its consequences for human mortality and public health and possible adaptation pathways. We discussed the need to accurately account for heat-related mortality during extreme heat episodes in the region (which is currently not done). This aspect could be of particular importance for discussions around “loss and damage” funds, accounting for the non-economic losses related to climate change. While the scientific community in general (and the TipESM work currently in progress) will help characterise changes in future dangerous episodes in which high human mortality is expected, it is necessary for governments to properly monitor and report the impacts.

An additional concern expressed by the government representatives from India is glacial melt and its impacts on energy production, which may reduce energy safety concurrently with the increased need for use of energy for cooling purposes. Moreover, issues surrounding transboundary water governance have been recognised as a significant challenge for the future.

Participants also stressed the importance of complementing discussions of climate risks and tipping points with practical and actionable solutions, including climate mitigation strategies and measures to protect communities from climate-related impacts. For example, participants expressed interest in discussions about how to meet increased energy demands sustainably. The exchange suggested that audiences may find the topic of climate tipping points difficult to engage with in the absence of constructive pathways for action and resilience-building and that clustering with projects working on solutions could be a helpful strategy.

The received input has been highly relevant to the TipESM work on climate impacts in WP7, as well as the wider TipESM community. Similarly, WP7 topics of food and water security, and WP6 topics of societal resilience, emerged as additional areas of significant concern, particularly regarding the cascading impacts that climate tipping points may have on vulnerable populations and regional stability.

Representatives from Brazil and Japan also reiterated the need for continued scientific exchange and accessible dialogue between researchers and policymakers. These discussions inspired the organisation of two follow-up online events, separately reported below, designed to address specific thematic priorities while providing additional opportunities for exchange, discussion, and participants' questions.

Follow-up online discussion with the UN Special Rapporteur on climate change and human rights on the topic of climate tipping points and food and water security

Following the policy briefing event held in Geneva, an online meeting between TipESM researchers and human rights experts was organised at the request of Prof. Elisa Morgera in support of the preparation of the Special Rapporteur's forthcoming report on food and water security.

The online meeting took place on March 23rd 2026. TipESM researchers Katty Huang and Andrew Hartley (METO), Marion Devillers from the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), Desislava Petrova (ISGlobal), and Paula Pacheco and Ivana Cvijanovic from (IRD) participated in the meeting. The discussion also included environmental law experts from the University of Exeter, Swansea University, University of Santiago de Compostela, and Ghent University, as well as representatives from the South Asia Regional Office of the OHCHR. The event was moderated by Dave-Inder Comar from Just Atonement Inc.

The majority of the meeting was dedicated to an interactive question-and-answer session, allowing legal and human rights experts to engage directly with TipESM scientists on issues related to climate tipping points, food security, water security, cascading impacts and human rights implications.

While it was acknowledged that uncertainties about the global warming levels associated with specific negative outcomes or tipping points still hamper the science-to-policy exchange, the feedback received by the researchers was to communicate their findings by emphasising both the risks of inaction and the limits of current scientific projections. For tipping points specifically and their adverse societal impacts, it was advised to consider the concept of foreseeable harm.

The discussion concluded with an interesting exchange on the rights of Indigenous Peoples affected by socio-environmental conflicts, followed by a short introduction to the Global Atlas of Environmental Justice. Just Atonement Inc. proposed establishing quarterly online meetings to sustain interdisciplinary dialogue and collaboration between the climate science and environmental law communities. We expect that these meetings will be feasible beyond the lifetime of TipESM.

Follow-up online discussion with representatives from the Brazilian Ministry of Environment and Climate Change and the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation

A short online workshop on climate change in the Amazon and tipping point risks was held on 23 April 2026 with representatives of the Brazilian government. Participants included staff from the Brazilian Ministry of Environment and Climate Change and the Brazilian Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation. The workshop addressed one of the TipESM project's focus areas relevant to the Brazilian government: the stability of the Amazon rainforest under climate change.

The programme included scientific presentations, a question-and-answer session, and a short co-design exercise aimed at identifying policy-relevant research priorities and information needs. Arthur Argles (METO) delivered a presentation entitled: "What Might Cause a Tipping Point in the Amazon Rainforest in the Future?" Desislava Petrova (ISGlobal) presented a talk entitled: "ENSO-Driven Climate and Vegetation Changes in the Amazon in Future Climate Simulations." These presentations were followed by a contribution from Marina Hirota from Federal University of Santa Catarina entitled "Indigenous Communities and the Need to Protect the Amazon Forest", which highlighted the perspectives and rights of Indigenous Peoples in the context of Amazon forest protection. An interactive session focused on identifying priority information needs and climate data requirements was facilitated by Ivana Cvijanovic from the French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development (IRD).

To support the workshop discussions, a short factsheet entitled "The Amazon: A Potential Tipping Point in the Earth's Climate System" was prepared with the help of ISGlobal's communication team and distributed to participants in advance of the meeting. The factsheet is publicly available on Zenodo.

A key message emerging from the discussion was the need to better understand the impacts of forest restoration efforts undertaken over the past four years. Participants noted that the Brazilian government has invested significant effort in reversing previous forest degradation and expressed strong interest in understanding whether these restoration measures are contributing to improved long-term forest stability. This feedback provides important advice for the future direction of TipESM research activities. In particular, it highlights the importance of complementing planned climate simulations that assess Amazon sensitivity to global warming and deforestation with analyses that examine the effects of forest recovery and restoration efforts. This input has been discussed with the researchers working on experiment protocols that study the Amazon stability.

More broadly, government representatives expressed significant concern about the ongoing decline of the Amazon rainforest and emphasised the importance of continued scientific exchange and policy-relevant reporting on this issue, particularly regarding the influence of the El Niño–Southern Oscillation (ENSO) on prolonged droughts that could affect Amazon stability. Approximately ten participants agreed to engage in a more detailed co-design exercise, the results of which are presented in the Annex part of the document. These findings will help inform both future Amazon-related research activities within TipESM (as well as the TIPMIP-BIOSPHERE research domain) and the development of the TipESM project’s risk register.

2.2 Cluster Science-Policy Forum with the European Commission

TipESM participated in a science-policy event with the European Commission, organised in collaboration with six other EU-funded projects of similar scientific focus: [ESM2025](#) (Earth system models for the future), [OptimESM](#) (Optimal High Resolution Earth System Models for Exploring Future Climate Change), [ClimTip](#) (Quantifying climate tipping points and their impacts), [RESCUE](#) (Response of the Earth System to overshoot, Climate neUtrality and negative Emissions) and [nextGEMS](#) (Next generation Earth-system Models).

Activity Description

A cluster of six projects (including TipESM) working on connected scientific topics of improved modelling and understanding future climate change delivered a science-policy meeting with the European Commission DGs RTD and CLIMA. A hybrid (online and in-person) meeting was held on 25 September 2025 in the DG RTD offices in Brussels. The meeting agenda was co-developed with DG RTD to ensure that projects were

responding to current needs and timely questions of interest to the commission. Project leads identified where they could contribute to the agenda topics and provided presentations.

Meeting Agenda

- 1. EU Climate Policy Overview – DG CLIMA**
- 2. General Context IPCC AR7 & preparations for CMIP7 and impact of project research**
- 3. Project results**
 - 3a. How can we track progress in the real world and anticipate risks?**
Including: the indicators of global climate change, the remaining carbon budget, and how much warming we are committed to.
 - 3b. How effectively will our mitigation actions result in a peak and decline in global warming?**
Including: the climate response to emissions, global warming response to net-zero or net-negative CO₂ emissions, the effectiveness of mitigation measures for CO₂ and CH₄, and under-delivery of land-based removals
 - 3c. Does a stable global climate also imply stable regional climates?**
Including: climate stabilisation and tipping points, Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation, Greenland ice sheet, abrupt changes and state transitions in CMIP6 simulations.
- 4. Outstanding knowledge gaps and research needs**
- 5. Lessons learned from EU project implementation**

One slide set was coordinated to cover all discussion topics, breaking down each section into 10-15-minute presentations, allowing plenty of time for questions on each subject.

DG RTD hosted the in-person meeting at the Champ De Mars building, and the DG Clima unit head provided an update on EU Climate policy. Five people representing the projects attended the meeting in person, whilst another 19 project participants and 14 participants from the EC (DEFIS, RTD, CLIMA, CINEA) were online. Prof. Shuting Yang from TipESM presented section (3c) of the agenda, which included TipESM, OptimESM and ClimTip research results. The information was presented as a readable set of slides that were afterwards circulated among the participants and posted on the TipESM website. The slides have been posted on Zenodo.

Photo 2: Online view of the cluster meeting with the European Commission.

Objectives

1. Detailed science briefing on understanding the indicators of global climate change, impacts of possible mitigation measures and climate stabilisation. From the TipESM side, Shuting Yang described how recent Earth system model simulations provide insights into key climate processes during warming, stabilisation, and cooling phases. The following scientific areas were the focus of the presentation:
 - Greenland Ice Sheet Stability.
 - Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) stability.
 - Atmospheric Circulation Response to Zero Emissions.
 - Abrupt changes and state transitions (especially in polar regions).
2. In collaboration with [ESM2025](#), [OptimESM](#), [TipESM](#), [ClimTip](#), [RESCUE](#), and [NextGEMS](#), the teams delivered a summary of key messages on tipping points suitable for policymakers. These specific messages were developed in the policy briefing document “Earth System Insights”.

Summary of key messages

- Climate processes relevant for regional climates**, such as land ice melting, ocean circulation and heat uptake, **will continue to change**, and **tipping points could still be crossed** even after reaching zero emissions.
- Regional climates will continue to change** under stable global temperatures. Generally, oceans will continue to warm and land areas will tend to cool, but regional differences are expected to be large.
- Changes will **affect weather patterns which will likely impact extremes**, but more research is needed to explore how extremes may change.
- Cities and rural regions will show pronounced differences** in their response to climate change.

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MOUSSON Mathilde (RTD)

Shuting Yang

Nico (RESCUE, OptimESM)

HJ +24

Fig. 3: Presentation of key messages during the cluster meeting with the European Commission.

Key Discussion Outcomes

Commission Heads of Units and their colleagues appreciated direct discussion between researchers and those who advise policymakers, suggesting that this is one of the most practical approaches for drawing research knowledge into policy. They found that clustering and working together across projects improved the clarity and uptake of messages during this science-policy meeting, providing a deeper perspective and overview of state-of-the-climate science compared with single-project briefings. We note that another clustering event is planned before the end of the project.

Specific questions included clarifications on recent emission trends, carbon removal potential, recent warming drivers, the representation and impacts of forest fires, the reliability of future climate change scenarios, the new IPCC reports, the impacts of the US withdrawal on research needs, and tool development needs.

This was also a valuable opportunity to discuss how to translate scientific outputs into policy-relevant tools. Researchers emphasised that translating scientific outputs into policy-relevant tools requires improved integration, coordination, and continuity across modelling communities and disciplines. Currently, Earth system models, integrated assessment models, and impact models operate too sequentially and

inconsistently, creating gaps between scientific results and usable policy insights. To address this, participants stressed the need for closer collaboration, consistent modelling frameworks (e.g. emissions-driven approaches), and improved “translation layers” that convert complex scientific outputs into actionable information. It was concluded that there is a need for more on-demand, policy-focused analyses, rather than slow, rigid research cycles, along with stronger engagement with policymakers to co-design relevant outputs. In terms of priorities, the discussion highlighted the importance of developing dedicated tools and capabilities for policy use, rather than embedding them indirectly within research projects. Some examples include: integrated, end-to-end modelling frameworks linking climate processes, socioeconomics, and impacts; emulators and simplified tools that can deliver fast, policy-relevant insights; quantitative synthesis and monitoring tools, especially for emissions, carbon removals, and tipping point risks; accessible platforms and services that translate large datasets into usable outputs for decision-makers. It was stressed that the long-term “legacy” mechanisms are needed to maintain tools and datasets beyond project lifetimes. Overall, it was concluded that policy support requires purpose-built, sustained capabilities and better coordination and not just improved scientific research outputs.

An interesting question on how research projects are engaging with growing political pressure to promote solar radiation management (SRM) was also raised. Researchers expressed significant concern about how SRM is entering policy debates, often framed as a fallback if mitigation fails. This has unintentionally strengthened its visibility and political appeal. Researchers highlighted that there is no clear or agreed-upon narrative yet on how to address SRM in research and policy contexts. It was reflected that even within the IPCC, there are ongoing debates about whether and how to include SRM in future outputs (e.g. the regional atlas), reflecting internal tensions. Many participants emphasised the need to develop a stronger, clearer scientific narrative and counter-arguments to prevent SRM from being seen as a viable substitute for mitigation.

It was concluded that it is essential for researchers to clearly communicate the need for mitigation strategies in the context of tipping points. This is especially relevant for projects like TipESM, where simulations representing different mitigation states are derived (the lower global warming level stabilisation and ramp-down simulations provide a counterfactual for the warmer global warming states).

3. Results Achieved

Policy Briefing Slide Decks and video presentation from the side event “Human Rights and Tipping Points”

Presentations used for the policy briefing event “Human Rights and Tipping Points” were developed with the help of ISGlobal’s communication team, led by Pau Rubio. TipESM project advisor, Robert Sweeney, also provided guidance for the development of legal audience-tailored presentation material. Following the event, the ISGlobal team helped us redevelop the presentations into Slide Decks. Presentation slides for the policy briefing event were purposely designed with minimal amounts of text. To better suit them as standalone outreach material, the original slides were afterwards enhanced with additional explanatory text and visuals. We refer to this material as Slide Decks. Three separate policy briefing Slide Decks have been developed.

The policy briefing event was recorded, and the video has been made publicly available on the TipESM webpage. The DMI project office, in collaboration with Just Atonement Inc., arranged the event recording and posted the video publicly.

Factsheet “The Amazon: a Potential Tipping Point in the Earth’s Climate System”

A factsheet on the Amazon tipping point was developed with the help of ISGlobal’s communications team for a subsequent follow-up meeting with the representatives from the Brazilian Environment and Climate Change, and the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation.

Policy Briefing Publication: “Earth System Highlights”

Key Earth system research insights used at the science-to-policy meeting with the European Commission were refined into a written policy briefing for broad dissemination, as summarised in the TipESM Communication and Dissemination Strategy (D9.2).

All derived material was widely distributed through the project’s websites, LinkedIn and Bluesky social media channels by the DMI’s project office.

4. Open Access

All the material produced for the policy briefing is publicly available and has been posted on Zenodo by the DMI's project office:

1. Policy Briefing Slide Deck #1 [Global climate tipping points: What are they and what could they mean?](#)
2. Policy Briefing Slide Deck #2 [The Amazon: A potential tipping point for the Earth's climate system"](#)
3. Policy Briefing Slide Deck #3 [Do we need a legal framework for loss of habitability due to extreme heat?](#)
4. Video Recording of the policy briefing event "Human Rights and Tipping Points":
 - ▶ Human Rights and Climate Tipping Points - side event at 61st session of the UN Human Rights Council
5. Factsheet [The Amazon: a Potential Tipping Point in the Earth's Climate System](#)
6. Policy Briefing Publication [Earth System Highlights](#)
7. Presentation from the ESM2025 clustering event [Climate and Earth System Insights and Advances](#)

5. Contribution to TipESM objectives

This deliverable contributes to achieving the following project objectives (SO).

SO8	To deliver a risk register of future TPs and a set of safe emission pathways to minimise the chance of crossing such TPs through engagement with stakeholders and by feeding tailored information to adaptation strategies via ClimateAdapt and the European Environmental Agency, European Climate and Health Observatory, ECDC, UN Offices. KPIs: A risk register of the likelihood of crossing climate TPs and their consequences for climate, ecosystems and society; safe future emissions pathways sampled by the project ESMs. (D8.1, D8.2, D8.3. Milestones: MS9, MS10)	Work packages: 1-7,8, and 9
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Our actions contribute to the development of the Risk Register by strengthening the understanding of stakeholder needs and priorities. The co-design event conducted with representatives of the Brazilian government provided valuable insights into stakeholder requirements related to Amazon forest stability, adaptation planning, and the need for more scientific evidence on successful forest restoration/mitigation efforts. This activity complements similar stakeholder engagement events previously organised by DMI (on Climate Atlas) and by SMHI (with the Swedish National Centre of Expertise on Climate Adaptation and with the network of climate adaptation contact points in public authorities), as described in earlier reports. Although not formally co-designed, valuable information was gained during the exchange with EC at the clustering event and exchange with government and non-government representatives at the policy briefing event in Geneva. Understanding the importance of this aspect, stakeholder engagement events are planned and will be reported on in the next reporting period.

S09	To provide policy guidance to the EC, IPCC, IPBES and the UNFCCC Global Stocktake, on the likelihood and consequences of crossing climate TPs and mitigation options to minimise the chance of such events. KPIs: A summary of the main project findings for non-specialists and leaflets highlighting potential impacts on a) human systems and society; b) ecosystems and biodiversity. (Deliverables: D9.2, D9.4, D9.5, D9.7, D10.1 and D10.2)	Work Packages: 1-8, and 9
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The first policy briefing has provided direct guidance to the European Commission representatives through a detailed scientific briefing on the physical science of tipping points, followed by a policy-oriented summary of key points. A second policy briefing event specifically engaged legal and governance communities, recognising their growing role in the interpretation and application of scientific evidence generated by the IPCC and related decision-making meetings such as UNFCCC’s COP meetings. Several TipESM researchers are also authors of the new IPCC report, and exchanges with the legal community and government representatives, along with their feedback, have provided valuable

guidance for researchers on both research design and the communication of findings (regarding their legal or decision-making implications).

To support knowledge transfer to non-specialist audiences and decision-makers, the project has produced a range of accessible dissemination materials. These currently include four policy briefs, one publicly available video recording, and one factsheet summarising key project findings in accessible language. The materials address potential impacts of climate tipping points on human systems and society, as well as on ecosystems, including implications for ecosystem stability and resilience.

These outputs directly contribute to the project KPI for communicating project findings to non-specialist stakeholders and policy audiences.

6. References

- (1) International Court of Justice: Obligations of States in respect of Climate Change (2025): <https://www.icj-cij.org/sites/default/files/case-related/187/187-20250723-adv-01-00-en.pdf>
- (2) Inter-American Court of Human Rights: Advisory Opinion on the climate emergency and human rights (2025): https://www.corteidh.or.cr/docs/opiniones/seriea_32_en.pdf
- (3) International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea: REQUEST FOR AN ADVISORY OPINION SUBMITTED BY THE COMMISSION OF SMALL ISLAND STATES ON CLIMATE CHANGE AND INTERNATIONAL LAW- ADVISORY OPINION (2024): https://www.itlos.org/fileadmin/itlos/documents/cases/31/Advisory_Opinion/C31_Adv_Op_21.05.2024_orig.pdf
- (4) United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. Paris Agreement. United Nations (2015): <https://treaties.un.org/pages/showDetails.aspx?objid=0800000280458f37https://unfccc.int/sites/d>

Annex: Summary of participants' input from the Amazon workshop

What knowledge from the TipESM project would be most useful for your work?

Which of these sectors your work is concerned with?

- 3 Environmental Management
- 6 Climate Impacts
- 4 Agriculture and Rural Development
- 5 Deforestation
- 6 Biodiversity
- 5 Water Resources
- 3 Disaster Risk Management
- 4 Traditional Communities and Indigenous Peoples
- 2 Bioeconomy

How do you currently use climate information in decision-making?

Which of the following factors are most relevant to your work?

Which future climate change impacts concern you the most?

In case you selected "other", please briefly describe ?

Which part(s) of the Amazon are most relevant for your work ?

Southern Amazon

The Arc of Deforestation

South Amazonas

South amazon

The BR 319 road region

On what time scales do you need climate information?

On what spatial resolution do you need climate information?

How useful is information on El Niño/La Niña future changes for your work?

- 100% Very useful
- 0% Somewhat useful
- 0% Not useful, I rather have information on specific impacts (temperatures, rainfall, etc.)
- 0% Unsure

What format would make climate information most usable for you?

What critical information is currently missing from scientific studies for your work?

What communities are being impacted by an extreme event, like a flood or a drought

Reports for policy makers

Reports

Specific vulnerability analysis

Information about solar radiation modification

Correlation between GEE Emission reduction and the efforts / policies ongoing

How concerned are you about large-scale Amazon forest collapse?

- 0 Not concerned - I don't think it can happen
- 0 Somewhat concerned
- 9 Very concerned
- 1 I don't have enough information to decide